

Enhancement of Digital Medical Image Analysis Performance using Deep Learning Technique

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Abstract— Medical image analysis systems based on AI and machine learning are desperately needed because of the growing amount of medical imaging data. Misdiagnosis and treatment delays may result from human error and variability in manual processing of medical imaging. In addition, the copious amount of medical picture data burdens medical personnel, delaying diagnosis and impairing patient care. These problems can be lessened by AI-driven systems, which offer more precise and effective picture analysis. In this article, a convolutional neural network classification model for medical image analysis was built. The iterative waterfall model was utilised in the study for the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC). After the image data has been prepared via segmentation and classification, the system trains a convolutional neural network (CNN) to provide a classification model for medical image analysis. When the accuracy and loss function were taken into account, the results showed a high success rate and a manageable error between the predicted and real features, suggesting the reliability of the classification model. The classification model provided an average accuracy of 99.01% and a loss function of 0.0112441 at an average each value of 170.

Keywords— Medical Imaging; Machine Learning; Deep Learning; Deep Learning; MRI; X-Ray; CT-Scan; Convolutional Neural Network

II. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 1)

In today's medical diagnosis and therapy, medical pictures are essential. As medical imaging technology advances, new types of medical image data such as radiology, medical ultrasound, and pathological images continue to emerge. These data give doctors access to a wealth of information and support them in developing precise diagnosis and treatment regimens (Sun et al., 2021). However, due to the limitations of equipment and technology used in the acquisition process, photographs may have noise, artefacts, low resolution, and other issues that lower their quality and usefulness (Wang et al., 2021).

Conventional approaches to medical picture reconstruction and enhancement frequently rely on mathematical models and signal processing methods including denoising, filtering, and interpolation (Wang, 2019). While these techniques can somewhat enhance the quality of the images, they frequently depend on manually created feature extractors and manually modified parameters, which make it challenging to apply these techniques to intricate and variable medical picture data. Furthermore, these techniques frequently struggle to handle

noise and intricate picture structures, which restricts their use in clinical settings (Gong et al., 2024).

According to Kim et al. (2018), medical image processing is a field of study that includes the development and use of algorithms and techniques for the analysis and interpretation of medical images. To support diagnosis, treatment planning, and therapeutic treatments, the main goal of medical image processing is to extract relevant information from medical pictures (Shen et al., 2015). picture segmentation, picture registration, feature extraction, classification, and visualisation are only a few of the many activities involved in medical image processing.

Medical image processing's main goal is to get relevant data from medical pictures in order to make diagnosis, treatment planning, and therapeutic treatments easier. Every modality has distinct advantages and disadvantages, and in order to extract meaningful information from the pictures created by various modalities, certain processing methods could be needed (Dhiman et al., 2022).

Medical image processing tools have transformed the medical sector by offering a non-invasive way to view and examine the body's interior structures and processes. It has made it possible to identify and diagnose illnesses early, schedule treatments accurately, and track how well those treatments are working. Medical image processing has greatly boosted patient care quality, decreased treatment costs, and improved patient outcomes (Li et al., 2023).

The study of processing, interpreting, and analysing medical pictures is known as medical image analysis (Guo et al., 2019). Since deep learning algorithms have been used more and more to improve the diagnosis, treatment, and monitoring of many medical disorders in recent years, the area of medical image analysis has seen a significant transition (Zhang et al., 2021). As a subfield of machine learning, deep learning involves training algorithms to extract knowledge from enormous amounts of data. Deep learning algorithms have the potential to automatically detect and classify abnormalities in a variety of medical imaging, such as X-rays, MRIs, CT scans, and ultrasound pictures (Van der Velden et al., 2022). Large datasets of annotated medical pictures, each with a label identifying the related medical disease or anomaly, may be used to train these algorithms (Suzuki, 2017).

After being taught, the algorithm can examine fresh medical pictures and give medical practitioners diagnostic information. Studies showing high levels of accuracy in identifying and diagnosing a wide range of medical disorders demonstrate the potential results of applying deep learning algorithms to medical picture analysis (Amiri et al., 2023a). As a result, several open-source and commercial software applications that use deep learning algorithms for medical picture analysis have been developed (Amiri et al., 2023b). All things considered, applying deep learning algorithms to medical image processing has the potential to significantly improve healthcare outcomes and change how medical imaging is used for diagnosis and treatment.

Within the field of machine learning, deep learning utilises artificial neural networks with several layers to identify and extract complex patterns from large-scale datasets (Zhang et al., 2014; Amiri et al., 2023c). It has revolutionised a number of fields, including speech recognition, computer vision, and natural language processing (Sudheer et al., 2019). The ability of deep learning to automatically extract features from unprocessed data removes the need for human feature engineering, which is one of its main benefits (Klang, 2018). Because of this, it is particularly effective in fields with big, complicated datasets, where conventional machine learning techniques would find it difficult to identify the underlying patterns (Altaf et al., 2019). Significant progress has also been made in a number of areas thanks to deep learning, such as picture and audio recognition, natural language understanding, and the creation of autonomous driving capabilities (Barragán-Montero et al., 2021). Therefore, the use of a deep learning model (CNN) to improve the performance of medical picture analysis is presented in this study.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

We have opted to utilise the iterative waterfall approach for the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC). The requirements analysis, system design, implementation, integration and testing, deployment, and maintenance stages are the sequential steps that make up the Waterfall technique, a conventional, linear approach to project management and software development. Before moving on to the next step, each one needs to be finished, and thorough documentation is required to guarantee traceability and clarity. This method has the advantage of having a clear framework and identifying problems early on, but it is rigid and presupposes fixed needs, which makes it difficult to adapt to changes and causes issue discovery to be delayed. Its rigidity makes it less desirable for dynamic projects where iterative approaches like Agile are more successful. However, it is appropriate for uncomplicated projects, regulated sectors, and stable surroundings.

A. Data Collection

There are high hopes for AI tools because most research to date on the application of deep learning to medical imaging have shown highly promising outcomes that frequently outperformed physicians' skills. Nevertheless, the majority of research employed limited training datasets, and the models that were

developed were not rigorously validated using a substantial amount of real-world test data. It is still uncertain if these deep learning models can be applied to new patients or to other therapeutic contexts.

The information utilised by this system is obtained from the Kaggle platform and includes pictures from CT, X-ray, ultrasound, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), among other tests. These images are sent in as input for the subsequent stage of the procedures. Having a sufficiently big training sample set with verified reference truth that is representative of the features of the population of interest is one of the fundamental prerequisites to construct a robust machine learning algorithm. Because a deep learning structure has an incredibly huge number of weights, training deep learning is significantly more difficult. The extent to which the training set is covered determines how generic the feature representations it has learnt, even using efficient regularisation techniques to minimise overfitting. More than 60 million weights make up AlexNet, while more than 1.2 million annotation-rich pictures make up the "ImageNet" training data set. It is expensive to collect representative patient-group medical imaging data with trustworthy annotation or reference truth. While gathering a large number of normal instances for a screening modality is generally simple, gathering enough abnormal cases can be challenging, particularly since the data set's various classifications should ideally be balanced.

B. Application of Deep learning for Medical Image Analysis

Based on some of the most important applications, medical image analysis uses deep learning algorithms to evaluate patients with a variety of medical conditions, including cancer, diabetic retinopathy, heart disease, lung nodule, brain tumour, foetal, thyroid, and prostate conditions (Moorthy and Gandhi, 2022). A few of the applications deal with various modalities, methods, and difficulties. Semantic segmentation is the process of identifying different areas of the image and classifying them into appropriate groups via segmentation. At the pixel level, segmentation may be viewed as a classification problem because of the low resolution required for segmentation.

In medical image analysis, segmentation has been a major area of study to identify complicated areas. One of the most extensively studied areas in the use of deep learning for medical image analysis is picture categorization. A classification task, which provides an overview of classification tasks using pattern recognition, essentially entails assigning three or more identifiers to the same data from a library of pre-determined classes. The detecting function, which entails locating the object of interest inside the image, combines the positioning and classification operations. An important area of computer-assisted diagnostic research is deep learning for automated medical systems. Image enhancement uses methods including background reduction, demising, and super-resolution to increase the quality of photographs. Processes like categorization, identification, and segmentation become more suitable as sharpness improves and might potentially provide a deep learning-based diagnostic visual upgrade.

The most fundamental method of artificial intelligence is deep learning. A deep learning technique builds an artificial neural network by using many layers. The input layer, hidden layer or layers, and output layer make up an artificial neural network (ANN) (Malhotra et al., 2019). The network's input layer receives the signal, the output layer decides how to use the input, and hidden layers in between the input and output layers carry out calculations (shown in Figure 1). Between the input and output layers of a deep neural network are several hidden layers.

Figure 1: Structure of Deep Learning model (Malhotra et al., 2022)

C. Segmentation

Semantic segmentation aims to classify different areas of an image into groups. The section may be viewed as a classification challenge at low resolution. Segmentation has been a key area of research for information extraction and is used in computer-aided diagnostics to extract anatomical regions. Here, we provide a summary of research segmentation techniques, the state of medical imaging segmentation techniques, problems they face, and potential fixes. The following is the algorithm that uses the edge-based segmentation approach to segment medical images:

Algorithm 1: Medical Image Segmentation

1. Step 1: Convert the input image to grayscale if it is not already
2. Step 2: Apply Gaussian Blur to smooth the image and reduce noise
3. Step 3: Compute the gradient magnitude and direction
4. Step 4: Apply Non-Maximum Suppression to thin the edges
5. Step 5: Apply Double Thresholding to determine potential edges
6. Step 6: Track edges by hysteresis to finalize edge detection
7. Convert RGB image to grayscale
8. Apply Gaussian Blur to the image
9. Compute gradients using Sobel operator
10. Thin the edges by applying non-maximum suppression
11. Determine the neighbouring pixels to compare with
12. Apply double thresholding
13. Finalize edges by hysteresis tracking
14. Check if the pixel has any strong edge neighbours

D. Classification

Another name for classification (CAD) is computer-aided diagnosis; the term "diagnostic" is often used to describe the

classification in medical imaging. In the assessment of medical imaging, the classifier is essential. One or more visuals are used as raw input throughout the categorization processing step, and an individual test factor is created as an output that describes the picture assessments. For multi-layered CNN models, a novel weight initialization and sliding window combination provides the basis for a recommended classification technique. The system outperforms other intelligent systems and conventional deep learning on several medical datasets. Numerous different types of pictures are used to train both the linear and non-linear CNNs.

E. Convolution Neural Network

The convolutional layer, pooling layer, and fully connected layer are the three primary neural layers that make up a convolutional neural network, or CNN (see Figure 2) (Dargan et al., 2019). Every layer plays a specific job. The convolution layer recognises discrete parts in a picture, such as edges or other visual components. The convolution layer multiplies an image pixel's local neighbours using kernels to carry out a mathematical operation. CNN convolves the provided picture using several kernels in order to produce its feature maps. The input data's spatial (width, height) dimensions are decreased for the neural network's subsequent layers by the pooling layer. The depth of the data is unaffected. We refer to this process as subsampling. The computing demands for subsequent layers are reduced by this reduction in size. In NN, high-level reasoning is performed by the fully linked layers. To offer the final results, these layers combine the different feature responses from the provided input image.

Figure 2: Architecture of CNN model (Malhotra et al., 2022)

F. Detection

This leads to the detecting function, which locates the object of interest inside the image by combining the categorization and positioning operations. An important area of computer-assisted diagnostic research is deep learning for automated medical systems. Such analytical methods often require the ability to identify a specific anatomical location. The most time-consuming task for experts is to find intriguing items inside categories. Typically, the goals involve finding and classifying microscopic illnesses over the whole picture domain.

G. Registration

Image registration is the process of combining two or more photos to offer additional features. Combining medical photos enhances their resolution, facilitating identification for medical professionals. It is crucial to merge data with other techniques since the medical image produced by a technology like CNN could not contain all of the information required by medical

specialists. For example, combining the input data yields more information than obtaining the data separately.

H. Image Enhancement

Image enhancement uses methods including background reduction, demising, and super-resolution to increase the quality of photographs. Processes like categorization, identification, and segmentation become more suitable as sharpness improves and might potentially provide a deep learning-based diagnostic visual improvement solution. Data preparation is necessary for demising techniques based on deep learning. With little data, the fully connected layer deep connected generating model worked effectively. Their method was able to recover data even under extreme conditions. A residual learning technique should be used to get over the drawbacks of small datasets. CNN receives the scans for categorization, and the contents of the files are made available to the general public. Classifying with tracking is the technique of visually localising each new step of diagnosis in an image by adding a zone of interest around the relevant area. Localization is the process of identifying the disease in the image. Anatomical localization is the pre-processing stage of a medical evaluation when the radiologist identifies certain important characteristics. The following is the presentation of the medical picture enhancement algorithm:

Algorithm 2: Medical Image Enhancement Algorithm

1. Start
2. Convert the input image to grayscale if it is not already
3. Apply Histogram Equalization to improve contrast
4. Apply Noise Reduction using a Gaussian filter
5. Apply Edge Enhancement using an Unsharp Mask
6. Adjust Intensity Levels using CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization)
7. Convert RGB image to grayscale
8. Apply histogram equalization to improve contrast
9. Apply Gaussian filter to reduce noise
10. Apply Unsharp Mask to enhance edges
11. Apply CLAHE to adjust intensity levels
12. Stop

I. Model Training

Using the deep learning toolkit in the MATLAB environment, the acquired and enhanced MRI data were divided into training, test, and validation sets before being loaded into the CNN architecture. The medical image's dimensions were determined using the input layer, which was followed by the formation of the first convolutional layer, the output of which is the CNN model, and the filter's scanning of the receptive fields. The output of the next three convolutional layers is similarly processed, flattened, and sent to the fully connected layer, which trained its neurons and produced a classification model for medical picture analysis using a back-propagation technique. Accuracy and loss function parameters were utilised to track training performance during the process, and the reported findings are covered in the following section.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 illustrates how a deep learning tool was used to closely monitor the CNN algorithm's performance after it was trained on medical data. Every epoch of the training process, assessment metrics including accuracy and loss were checked. A target accuracy and loss function value of around 100% and 0%, respectively, were to be reached, signifying that all samples were properly identified by the algorithm and that there was little difference between the real and predicted labels. Analysing the performance shown in Figure 2, it was found that at epoch 186, the CNN algorithm attained a low loss function value of 0.03413 and an amazing accuracy of 99%. This suggests that the model did a very good job of minimising the discrepancy between the anticipated and real labels and correctly identifying the medical imaging data. These outcomes demonstrate how well the trained CNN algorithm uses medical data to classify and analyse medical pictures. The model's capacity to recognise and learn pertinent patterns and characteristics from the medical pictures is demonstrated by the high accuracy and low loss values attained, which allow for precise analysis and classification of medical images. Figure 3 displays the system's performance outcome.

Figure 3: Result of CNN testing

As indicated in Table 1, the CNN model was initially validated using the ten-fold cross validation technique, which produced an average accuracy, loss function, and epoch for the classification model's evaluation and generation.

TABLE I. TENFOLD VALIDATION PERFORMANCE

Iteration	ACC%	MSE	Epoch
1	98.9	0.0034534	
2	99.0	0.0064543	137
3	99.1	0.0026540	189
4	98.8	0.0053505	163
5	99.3	0.0056400	180
6	98.9	0.0056420	155
7	99.7	0.0046459	129
8	98.9	0.0045647	178
9	98.6	0.0034515	190
10	98.9	0.0705542	189
Average	99.01	0.011241	169.6

The classification model provided an average accuracy of 99.01% and a loss function of 0.0112441 at an average each value of 170, according to the results in Table 1. The result's implications demonstrated that, when utilised to train CNN with a high success rate, the classification model can successfully analyse medical pictures.

V. CONCLUSION

Although deep learning has significantly advanced medical image analysis, its practical applicability is still limited by the effects of picture categorization, segmentation, and registration. It has demonstrated encouraging outcomes in terms of

processing power and the improvement in usable structured data availability. But even before automatic procedures are put into place, a lot of obstacles need to be removed. New technologies that are tailored to certain jobs can be used, and many frameworks for creating profound learning systems exist; they were discussed here. Low segmentation resolution, low image attractiveness, and low classification accuracy are just a few of the problems in the field of medical image analysis that deep learning has been specifically developed to address and address.

Based on the assessment, deep learning methods can examine different data sets to develop deep learning frameworks and applications that will help improve image enhancement using convolutional neural networks, increase resolution through segmentation, and improve classification accuracy. New models with higher accuracy can yet be created because deep learning technology is still in its infancy. Aside from this, the modelling and diagnostic sub-domains might use some enhancement. Future research must stay on course to eventually increase the efficacy of illness detection methods if convolutional neural networks are to be employed in the identification of medical conditions. In this article, a convolutional neural network classification model for medical image analysis was built. The iterative waterfall model was utilised in the study for the System Development Life Cycle (SDLC). After the image data has been prepared via segmentation and classification, CNN is used to train the system and create a classification model for medical image analysis. When the accuracy and loss function were taken into account, the results showed a high success rate and a manageable error between the predicted and real features, suggesting the reliability of the classification model. The classification model provided an average accuracy of 99.01% and a loss function of 0.0112441 at an average each value of 170, according to the

results in Table 1. The present medical picture data sets are tiny in size. When deep learning models are formed, overfitting problems arise because deep learning algorithms require a large amount of data set support for training.

REFERENCES

- [46] Altaf F., Islam S., Akhtar N., & Janjua N., (2019) Going deep in medical image analysis: concepts, methods, challenges, and future directions. *IEEE Access*. (2019) 7:99540–72. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2929365
- [47] Amiri Z., Heidari A., Darbandi M., Yazdani Y., Jafari N., & Esmaeilpour M., (2023a) The personal health applications of machine learning techniques in the internet of behaviors. *Sustainability*. 15:12406. doi: 10.3390/su151612406
- [48] Amiri Z., Heidari A., Navimipour N., & Unal M., (2023b) Resilient and dependability management in distributed environments: a systematic and comprehensive literature review. *Clust Comput*. 26:1565–600. doi: 10.1007/s10586-022-03738-5
- [49] Amiri Z., Heidari A., Navimipour N., Unal M., & Mousavi A., (2023c) Adventures in data analysis: a systematic review of deep learning techniques for pattern recognition in cyber-physical-social systems. *Multimed Tools Appl*. 2023:1–65. doi: 10.1007/s11042-023-16382-x
- [50] Barragán-Montero A., Javaid U., Valdés G., Nguyen D., Desbordes P., & Macq B., (2021) Artificial intelligence and machine learning for medical imaging: a technology review. *Phys Med*. (2021) 83:242–56. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmp.2021.04.016
- [51] Dargan S., Kumar M., Ayyagari M., & Kumar G., (2019) A survey of deep learning and its applications: a new paradigm to machine learning. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, vol. 27, pp. 1–22, 2019.
- [52] Dhiman G., Juneja S., Viriyasitavat W., Mohafez H., Hadizadeh M., & Islam M., (2022) A novel machine-learning-based hybrid CNN model for tumor identification in medical image processing. *Sustainability*. (2022) 14:1447. doi: 10.3390/su14031447
- [53] Gong Y., Qiu H., Liu X., Yang Y., & Zhu M., (2024) Research and Application of Deep Learning in Medical Image Reconstruction and Enhancement. *Frontiers in Computing and Intelligent Systems* ISSN: 2832-6024 | Vol. 7, No. 3, 2024
- [54] Guo Z., Li X., Huang H., Guo N., & Li Q., (2019) Deep learning-based image segmentation on multimodal medical imaging. *IEEE Trans Radiat Plasma Med Sci*. (2019) 3:162–9. doi: 10.1109/TRPMS.2018.2890359
- [55] Kim J., Hong J., & Park H., (2018) Prospects of deep learning for medical imaging. *Precis. Future Med*. (2018) 2:37–52. doi: 10.23838/pfm.2018.00030
- [56] Klang E., (2018) Deep learning and medical imaging. *J Thorac Dis*. (2018) 10:1325–8. doi: 10.21037/jtd.2018.02.76
- [57] Li M., Jiang Y., Zhang Y., & Zhu H., (2023) Medical image analysis using deep learning algorithms. *Front. Public Health* 11:1273253. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1273253
- [58] Malhotra P., Gupta S., & Koundal D., (2019) Computer aided diagnosis of pneumonia from chest radiographs. *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 4202–4213, 2019.
- [59] Malhotra P., Gupta S., Koundal D., Zaguia A., & Enbeyle W., (2022) Deep Neural Networks for Medical Image Segmentation. *Hindawi Journal of Healthcare Engineering* Volume 2023, Article ID 9781975, 1 page <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9781975>
- [60] Moorthy J., & Gandhi U., (2022) A Survey on Medical Image Segmentation Based on Deep Learning Techniques. *Big Data Cogn. Comput*. 2022, 6, 117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc6040117>
- [61] Shen D., Wu G., Zhang D., Suzuki K., Wang F., & Yan P., (2015) Machine learning in medical imaging. *Comput Med Imaging Graph*. (2015) 41:1–2. doi: 10.1016/j.compmedimag.2015.02.001
- [62] Sudheer K., & Shoba B., (2019) Medical image analysis using deep learning: a systematic literature review In: AK Somani, S Ramakrishna, A Choudhary, C Choudhary and B Agarwal, editors. *Emerging Technologies in Computer Engineering: Microservices in big data analytics: Second international conference, ICETCE 2019*. Jaipur, India: Springer (2019). 81–97
- [63] Sun T., Wang X., Lin D., Bao R., Jiang D., & Ding B., (2021). Medical image security authentication method based on wavelet reconstruction and fractal dimension. *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks*, 17(4), 1-33.
- [64] Suzuki K., (2017) Overview of deep learning in medical imaging. *Radiol Phys Technol*. (2017) 10:257–73. doi: 10.1007/s12194-017-0406-5
- [65] Van der Velden B., Kuijf H., Gilhuijs K., & Viergever M., (2022) Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) in deep learning-based medical image analysis. *Med Image Anal*. (2022) 79:102470. doi: 10.1016/j.media.2022.102470
- [66] Wang G., (2019). High temporal-resolution dynamic pet image reconstruction using a new spatiotemporal kernel method. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, 38(3), 664-674.
- [67] Wang Y., Ge X., Ma H., Qi S., & Yao Y., (2021) Deep learning in medical ultrasound image analysis: a review. *IEEE Access*, 2021(99), 1-1.
- [68] Zhang D., Wu G., & Zhou L., (2014) *Machine learning in medical imaging*. Berlin: Springer.
- [69] Zhang Y., Gorriz J., & Dong Z., (2021) Deep learning in medical image analysis. *J Imaging*, 7:74. doi: 10.3390/jimaging7040074